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IMPROVING THE ENVIRONMENTAL AND OPERATIONAL PROPERTIES OF LOW-OCTANE GASOLINE

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Abstract. This article reflects on improving the environmental and operational properties of low-octane gasoline.

Key words: fuel oil, motor gasoline, petroleum product.

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ И ЭКСПЛУАТАЦИОННЫХ СВОЙСТВ НИЗКООКТАНОВОГО БЕНЗИНА

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматриваются вопросы улучшения экологических и эксплуатационных свойств низкооктанового бензина.

Ключевые слова: мазут, автомобильный бензин, нефтепродукты.

Currently, motor gasoline is the most widely known and widespread petroleum product. One third of the oil produced worldwide is processed into motor gasoline. In the near future, the value of motor gasoline will remain.

One of the main problems of environmental safety of the population is the negative impact of motor vehicles on the environment and public health.

Reducing the negative impact of cars on the environment is achieved primarily by improving engines and tightening standards for emissions with exhaust gases.

The concept of "environmentally friendly motor fuels" covers a wide range of fuel characteristics: reducing the sulfur content, introducing oxygenates, reducing the content of benzene and other aromatic and olefin hydrocarbons, increasing the octane numbers of gasoline and the use of an additive package.

Recently, in order to save oil fuels, fusel oil (CM) has been added to them - a by-product of rectification of ethyl alcohol, which is a mixture of low molecular weight alcohols and a small amount of other organic compounds [1].

Analysis of existing methods of utilization of fusel oil, which accumulates in large quantities at alcohol industry enterprises, has shown that fusel oil can be used to produce industrial alcohols, as a catalyst in the microbiological industry in the production of feed yeast, in some chemical technologies (during graphite flotation, to obtain classifiers, etc.)

There is information in the literature [2] about the use of fusel oil as an additive to diesel fuel and fuel oil for heating systems. The advantages of its use are low cost and utilization of waste from the alcohol industry.

Studies conducted at the ANC ITMO NASB [2] have shown that fusel oil, according to its characteristics, can be attributed to a fuel that does not pollute the environment (Table 1).

Table 1

Characteristics of hydrocarbon fuels

Parameters	Fuel		
	Fuel oil	Diesel fuel	Fusel oil
Density, kg/m ³	960-1030	930-970	830-840
Viscosity, sSt	59-118	3,5-6,0	5,5-5,8
Flash point, °C	90-140	40-60	37-40
Ignition temperature, °C	385	240-370	400
Combustion temperature, kcal/kg	9500-9700	9500-10200	8000-8200

It should be noted that according to its parameters, this fusel oil is heavy and closest to diesel fuel. The tests of thermal engineering and environmental indicators of the boiler of heating systems carried out by the same authors when working on 100% fusel oil and 100% diesel fuel gave almost the same result. It has been established that fusel oil is equivalent to diesel fuel in its thermophysical, technological and thermomechanical characteristics, but much cheaper than the latter: when fusel oil is burned, the ecology of the environment improves due to the fact that the exhaust gas consists only of CO₂, H₂O and oxidized nitrogen of the air.

In this paper, the possibility of increasing the concentration of fusel oil to 35% is considered when it is added to AI-80 gasoline [3,4].

The qualitative and quantitative composition of fusel oil was established by gas-liquid chromatography [5] and the following composition was identified in it (Table 2).

Table 2

Qualitative and quantitative composition of fusel oil

Alcohols	Composition, % mass
N- propyl	3,69
Iso – propyl	5,90
Butyl	7,50
Iso – butyl	8,76
Mixture of isoamyl alcohols	68,48
Impurity	5,67

Mixtures of gasoline with fusel oil with concentrations of 5,10,15,20,25,30 and 35% by weight were prepared and octane numbers were determined for them on a single-cylinder universal unit UIT-85.

The following results were obtained (Table 3).

Table 3

Changing the anti-knock properties of low-octane gasoline AI-80 with the addition of fusel oil

Gasoline mixture + CM	octane number	Octane number increase	Δ octane number	% Increase in octane number
Gasoline + 5 % CM	82,6	2,6	2,3	3,25
Gasoline + 10 % CM	84,9	4,9	2,3	6,15
Gasoline + 15 % CM	87,2	7,2	1,8	9,0

Gasoline + 20 % CM	89,0	9,0	1,4	11,25
Gasoline + 25 % CM	90,4	10,4	1,7	13,00
Gasoline + 30 % CM	92,1	12,1	1,8	15,75
Gasoline + 35 % CM	93,9	13,9	-	17,35

As can be seen from the above data, the improvement of anti-knock indicators of mixed fuel takes place in the entire range of fusel oil concentrations. However, if we consider the data obtained from the standpoint of the value of the increments of octane number (Δ octane number), it can be seen that at first the highest values of Δ octane number occur, which then decrease somewhat in the area of the addition of large concentrations of fusel oil, especially a noticeable drop in Δ octane number with 25% addition of fusel oil to gasoline.

From the data obtained, it follows that to improve the anti-knock properties and increase the resource of gasoline, it is possible to add up to 25% fusel oil to AI-80 gasoline.

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